

Customization of Requirements

- User Manual -

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1. Introduction

The Customization of Requirements functionality in MEDINA is provided by the *CNL Editor* tool. *CNL Editor* is a Web application, accessible via an Internet browser, which allows to view the Requirement and Obligations (REO) defined for Cloud Services and to make some changes to them.

A REO is an association between the Requirement, or Security Control, and a set of policies (or Obligations), where are specified the rules that must be applied to a Cloud Service *ResourceType* for the compliancy of Requirement itself.

A REO for a specific Cloud Service Id (CS_Id) is created by the *NL2CNL Translator*¹ with the aid of the *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics*² and Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. This process starts in the *Orchestrator*³, where the user can select a list of requirements to customize. The *Orchestrator* invokes the *NL2CNL Translator*, which aims to: associate a set of metrics to a requirement, translate metrics into obligations and store a requirement and its associated metrics into a REO object in the CNL Store.

A REO obligation is defined as follows:

ResourceType MUST MetricName TargetValueType (Operator, TargetValue)

As an example:

VirtualMachine MUST MalwareProtectionOutput Boolean (==, true)

Users can see and act on the REOs that are pertaining to those cloud services that are included in their Keycloak profile (filtering on Cloud Service Id).

A user can modify a REO by deleting Obligations, changing the operator, or updating the *TargetValue* of the metric to customize it for a specific Cloud Service Provider instead of using the default value (i.e., the value defined in the *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics*).

CNL Editor has a vocabulary containing an Ontology to control the selection of the operator and in some cases the definition of *TargetValues*. It also includes internal databases to store REO files and data.

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to *CNL Editor* is managed by Keycloak⁴. Only authorized users can invoke the tool within the MEDINA IUI (Integrated User Interface). The visibility of the REO, and their eventual management, is allowed depending on Cloud Service Id, i.e., a user can show and manage a REO if its Keycloak profile contains the Cloud Service Id associated to that REO.

At the time of writing this manual, we are considering, as an enhancement to the *CNL Editor*, the implementation of the Role Authorization feature as specified in the following table:

¹ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D2.5 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927213>

² For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D2.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794478>

³ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D3.6 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225>

⁴ <https://www.keycloak.org>

Role	UI Actions
IT Security Governance	Read
Security Analyst	Read
Domain Governance	Read
Product and Service Owner	Read
Product (Security) Engineer	Show/Edit/Complete/Map to CNL Editor UI
Chief Information Security Office (CISO)	Read
Customer	None
Auditor	Read

Thus, a user with “Read” role will only be able to “Show” REOs and a user with “Write” Role [Product (Security) Engineer] will be authorized to perform all available operations on REOs, described in this manual.

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

CNL Editor includes a toolbar (see Figure 1), always accessible in the upper area. The *Help* button allows the user to get to the user manual.

Figure 1. CNL Editor toolbar

2.2. List of REOs

The user invokes the *CNL Editor* in the MEDINA UI by selecting the “Customization of Requirements” left menu option. The web page in Figure 2 is displayed showing the list of all REOs filtered by Cloud Service Id (CS-Id).

Figure 2. List of REOs

For each REO, the tool displays this metadata:

- **Name:** Description name of the REO.

- **Creator:** User that created the REO through the *Orchestrator*, with the help of *NL2CNL Translator* (to associate a set of metrics to a requirement, translate metrics into obligations and store REO).
- **Status:** Status of the REO (see Figure 3), which can have one of the following values:
 - *Customised*: the REO has been changed but has not been declared as completed by the user.
 - *Completed*: the REO was declared as completed by the user, so the *Map* operation (invocation to *DSL Mapper*⁵) can be performed on it to translate the REO into Rego code⁶.
 - *Available*: the REO was translated into Rego code after the execution of the *Map* operation.

Figure 3. REO status diagram

- **Creation Date:** Date of creation of the REO.
- **ID:** Universal Unified ID of the REO.
- **Cloud Service ID:** Cloud Service Id for which the REO has been defined.

When the user selects a REO, a menu appears on the right-hand side of the web page showing the operations allowed on the REO according to its status (see Figure 4 and Figure 5). The available Operations are:

- **Show:** Visualizes the REO details.
- **Edit:** Allows editing of the REO (only available for “Customised” or “Available” REO status)
- **Map:** Invokes *DSL Mapper* that translates the Obligation into Rego code (only available for “Completed” REO status).
- **Copy:** Duplicates the REO.
- **Raw:** Shows, in .xml format, the file contained in the internal database with the REO data.
- **Delete:** Removes the REO from the internal database.

⁵ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D2.5 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927213>

⁶ <https://www.openpolicyagent.org/>

- **Cancel:** Makes the visualization come back to the List of REOs.

Figure 4. Operations available on a selected REO (status “Customised”)

Figure 5. Operations available on a selected REO (status “Completed”)

The following explains the main operations on REOs: *Show*, *Edit* and *Map*.

2.2.1. Show operation

The *Show* operation allows the user to view the details of the REO on a web page consisting of two sections: “Metadata” and “Obligations”.

The “Metadata” section shows information about the REO (see Figure 6), such as vocabulary version, Requirement, Security Control, Cloud Service, Framework (e.g., EUCS), Metric type (Technical or Organizational), and Assurance level (High, Medium, Low).

Figure 6. Show the details of a REO: Metadata section

The “Obligations” section shows all policies defined for the requirement, indicating their origin (*catalogue*⁷ or *recommender*⁸) on the right-hand side. Policies follow the statement format described in section 1.

Figure 7. Show the details of a REO: Obligation section

Finally, the *Back* button allows the user to come back to the REO list.

2.2.2. Edit operation

When the user selects the *Edit* operation for a REO, the tool shows a web page with all REO data and the possibility to make changes to it (see Figure 4). The *Edit* operation page, as seen above for the *Show* operation page, also includes two sections: “Metadata” and “Obligations” (see Figure 8 and Figure 9).

⁷ ‘catalogue’ indicates that the metric comes from the *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics* tool.

⁸ ‘recommender’ refers that the metric comes from by the Metric recommender, which is a component of the *NL2CNL Translator* tool.

Figure 8. Edit a REO: Metadata section

Figure 9. Edit a REO: Obligations section

The user can perform two actions on an Obligation (see Figure 10):

- delete the Obligation by clicking on the button
- change the Obligation parameters by clicking on the *Add info* button

Figure 10. Edit a REO: changing the Operator and/or the TargetValue for an Obligation

where *Param* is the Operator, and *Option* is the TargetValue.

Finally, the user can select one of the following buttons (see Figure 8):

- **Update:** Confirms changes and maintains the REO in “Customised” status.
- **Complete:** Confirms changes and pass the REO status from “Customised” to “Completed”.
- **Back:** Cancels the changes and exits from the *Edit* operation, so the visualization comes back to the List of REOs.

2.2.3. Map operation

With the selection of the *Map* operation, which is only available for REOs in the “Completed” status, the policies contained in the REO are translated into Rego code and can be used by the *Orchestrator*⁹.

If the *Map* operation is completed with success, the REO goes from “Completed” to “Available” status, otherwise the message “Failed to Map” is displayed for a few seconds in the lower right corner of the page (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Map of a REO: failed operation

⁹ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D3.6 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225>

3. Delivery and usage

3.1. Licensing information

The *CNL Editor* is offered under the Apache 2.0 license and is a proprietary tool of HPE.

3.2. More information

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables and blog posts related to the *CNL Editor*.